

Possible Antifungal Agents

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A number of substituted amides and amino esters of undec 10-enoic acid as well as secondary and tertiary amines containing 10-undecenyl group was synthesised. 10-Undecenyl 1-indanyl amine exhibited antifungal activity against *M. canis* and *C. neoformans*.

UNDECENOIC acid and its salts are used against antifungal diseases¹. In absence of the knowledge of the mechanism of antifungal activity of these substances a number of its derivatives of types I, II, III, IV and V have been prepared for testing their antifungal activity.

I

II

III

IV

V

VI

Compounds of the types I, II, III and IV have been prepared by the interaction of undecenoic acid

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	R-NHCO(CH ₂) ₈ CH = CH ₂ (I)			%N ₂	
		% Yield	B.p. (mm) or m.p., °C	Mol. Formula	Found	Calc.
1	CH ₃	99	44-45 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₂₃ ON	7.4	7.1
2	C ₂ H ₅	96	178(3) 35-37	C ₁₃ H ₂₅ ON	6.9	6.63
3	C ₃ H _{7-n}	81	185 (1.5)	C ₁₄ H ₂₇ ON	6.4	6.22
4	C ₄ H _{9-n}	90	195 (1.5)	C ₁₅ H ₂₉ ON	5.7	5.86
5	C ₈ H _{13-n}	90	255 (2)	C ₁₇ H ₃₃ ON	5.6	5.24
6	1-Indanyl	80	60-61 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ ON	4.5	4.68
7	1-(1, 2, 3, 4-Tetrahydro-naphthyl).	53	68 ^a	C ₂₁ H ₃₁ ON	4.7	4.47
8	C ₂ H ₅ OCOCH ₂ -	98	195-97 (0.8)	C ₁₅ H ₂₇ ON	5.6	5.2

^a = crystallised from alcohol.

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TABLE 1—Contd.

Sl. No.	R	% Yield	B.p. (mm) or m.p., °C	Mol. Formula	%N ₂	
					Found	Calc.
9	CH ₃	94	106 (2)	C ₁₃ H ₂₅ ON	6.7	6.63
10	C ₂ H ₅	73	162-64 (1.5)	C ₁₅ H ₂₉ ON	6.1	5.86
11	C ₃ H _{7-n}	81	181 (2.5)	C ₁₇ H ₃₃ ON	5.5	5.24
12	C ₄ H _{9-n}	86	190 (1.5)	C ₁₉ H ₃₇ ON	5.1	4.74
$\begin{array}{c} \text{R} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHCO}(\text{CH}_2)_6-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2 \text{ (III)} \\ \diagup \\ \text{R} \end{array}$						
13	C ₂ H ₅	90	199-200 (1)	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ ON ₂	10.2	9.9
$\text{R}-\text{CO}_2(\text{CH}_2)_6-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2 \text{ (IV)}$						
14	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2- \\ \diagup \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}$	50	150-52 (0.8)	C ₁₅ H ₂₉ O ₂ N	5.8	5.49
15	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \qquad \qquad \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \qquad \qquad \diagup \\ \text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}- \\ \diagup \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}$	77	175-77 (1)	C ₁₆ H ₃₁ O ₂ N	5.5	5.2
16	$\begin{array}{c} \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2- \\ \diagup \\ \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \end{array}$	66	170 (1.5)	C ₁₇ H ₃₃ O ₂ N	5.1	4.9
17	$\begin{array}{c} \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2- \\ \diagup \\ \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \end{array}$	95	205 (1)	C ₁₈ H ₃₅ O ₂ N	5.1	4.71
18	$\begin{array}{c} \text{C}_4\text{H}_9 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2- \\ \diagup \\ \text{C}_4\text{H}_9 \end{array}$	82	191-93 (0.8)	C ₂₁ H ₄₁ O ₂ N	4.4	4.13
$\text{RHN}(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2 \text{ (V)}$						
19	CH ₃	70	95-97 (1.0)	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ N	7.8	7.65
20	C ₂ H ₅	75	95-97 (0.8)	C ₁₃ H ₂₇ N	7.4	7.1
21	C ₃ H _{7-n}	70	107-9 (1)	C ₁₄ H ₂₉ N	6.9	6.63
22	C ₄ H _{9-n}	72	107-9 (0.8)	C ₁₅ H ₃₁ N	6.5	6.22
23	1-Indanyl	70	98-99 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ NCl (hydrochloride)	4.7	4.35
^a = Hydrochloride, crystallised from pet. ether (40-60)						
$\begin{array}{c} \text{R} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}-(\text{CH}_2)_6-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2 \text{ (VI)} \\ \diagup \\ \text{R} \end{array}$						
24	CH ₃	82	105 (2.5)	C ₁₃ H ₂₇ N	7.4	7.1
25	C ₂ H ₅	95	110-12 (1)	C ₁₅ H ₃₁ N	6.0	6.22
26	C ₃ H _{7-n}	98	125-27 (1)	C ₁₇ H ₃₅ N	5.7	5.53
27	C ₄ H _{9-n}	72	146-48 (0.8)	C ₁₉ H ₃₉ N	5.2	4.98

chloride with the appropriate amine or amino alcohol. Reduction of the amides with LAH yielded the amines of the type V.

*Test Report*² : Antifungal properties were assayed *in vitro* against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporum canis* and *Cryptococcus neoformans*. None of the compounds except compound No. 23 enlisted in Table 1, inhibited growth at a conc. of 12.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Compound No. 23 inhibited growth of *M. canis* and *C. neoformans* at conc. of 3.13 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

Experimental

Undecenoic acid amides (I, II, III) :

Method A : Undec-10-enoic acid chloride (0.04 mol) was added under stirring to an appropriate amine (0.09 mol) at 10°–15°. After the reaction was over, the mass was acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with alkali, ether layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and distilled. Data are recorded in Table 1. Compounds No. 1 to 12 were prepared by this method.

Method B : Undec-10-enoic acid chloride (0.04 mol) was added under stirring to an appropriate amine

(0.05 mol) at 10° to 15°. After the reaction was over, the mass was made alkaline with dil. caustic soda and the amide or ester extracted out with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and distilled. Data are listed in Table 1. Compounds No. 13 to 18 were prepared by this method.

1-Dialkylamino undec-10-ene (V) : The amide (I or II) (0.02 mol dissolved in 30 ml anhydrous ether) was added slowly into a suspension of LAH (0.03 mol in 100 ml. ether) and the mixture was refluxed for a period of 60 hr. The mass was then decomposed with water, added dropwise, and the ethereal solution was extracted out with dil. HCl. The acid solution was basified and the liberated amine was extracted out with benzene. Benzene solution was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and distilled. Data are listed in Table 1.

References

1. BRITISH PHARMACOPOEIA, The Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1968, p. 1057.
2. Test report was kindly furnished by Messrs Bristol Laboratories, Syracuse, U.S.A.